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List of Acronyms

3D	Three Dimension
AI	Artificial Intelligence
AIOps	AI Operations
AR	Augmented Reality
CD	Continuous Delivery
CI	Continuous Integration
6DoF	Six Degrees of Freedom
FPS	Frame per Second
HD	High Definition
HTC	Holographic-Type Communications
KPI	Key Performance Indicator
MEC	Multi-access Edge Computing
ML	Machine Learning
MLOps	Machine Learning Operations
NFV	Network Function Virtualization
NR	New Radio
QoE	Quality of Experience
RAN	Radio Access Network
SoA	State-of-the-Art
TD	Technological Domain
UE	User Equipment
UNICO	Universalización de Infraestructuras Digitales para la Cohesión
VNF	Virtual Network Function
VR	Virtual Reality
XR	Extended Reality

Executive Summary

Holoportation is a technology that allows for real-time, three-dimensional telepresence. It uses a combination of three dimensional (3D) capture technology, edge computing, and AI algorithms to transmit a person's likeness in real-time to a remote location. Edge AI plays a crucial role in this technology by enabling the real-time processing of the 3D data captured by the cameras, and running the AI algorithms that are used to reconstruct and transmit the 3D image of the person. The use of edge AI also allows for a low-latency, high-fidelity transmission of the holoportation data, which is essential for creating a seamless telepresence experience. One of the main advantages of Edge AI in holoportation is that it allows for the use of the technology in environments with limited or unreliable internet connectivity, such as remote or rural areas.

Specifically, it can be deduced that besides the standard network requirements, such as high bandwidth, necessary for supporting holographic teleportation, data synchronisation will also be crucial in ensuring a high-quality user experience, especially in cases of teleportation operations that are based on multiple sources.

On the other hand, as an enabler of the holoportation service, intelligent orchestration is based on AIOps framework to manage the lifecycle of AI models by continuously monitoring their performance, triggering retraining as necessary, and efficiently delivering the relevant artifacts to the appropriate technological domains (TDs), swiftly adapting to changes in the service dynamics and reducing the reaction time and thereby the latency.

This deliverable E2.1 of 6GENABLERS, IA para 6G: Ultra Automatización y Optimización, reference number TSI-063000-2021-10, hereinafter referred to as 6GENABLERS-AI, describes the functional and non-functional requirements of the holoportation use-case. After revisiting the state-of-the art (SoA) of holographic-type communications (HTC) and analysing the existing gaps in terms of communication as well as intelligent orchestration, the deliverable details the use case setup, service dependencies, use-case architecture and the role of AIOps. The use case requirements and key performance indicators (KPIs) are afterward listed and analysed.

1 Introduction

Recently, holographic teleportation has been seen as the next generation of immersive conferencing applications, where the supported 6-degree-of-freedom (6DoF) will allow end users to freely move in the virtual scene. In addition to the support of immersive inter-person communication services, 6G holographic teleportation will undoubtedly become a key enabler for the vertical markets such as gaming/entertainment, education, healthcare, tourism and many others. Specifically, holoportation would allow:

- Remote collaboration: Holoportation could enable remote teams to work together in a more immersive and natural way, allowing them to see and interact with each other in 3D as if they were in the same physical space.
- Distance learning: Holoportation could enable students to attend classes and lectures remotely in a more engaging and interactive way, allowing them to see and interact with their teachers and classmates in 3D.
- Virtual reality: Holoportation could enable users to interact with each other and their environment in a more realistic and natural way, creating a more immersive and interactive virtual reality experience.
- Telemedicine: Holoportation could enable doctors to provide more personal and effective consultations with patients remotely, allowing them to see and interact with patients in 3D as if they were in the same room.
- Social interactions: Holoportation could enable people to interact with each other in a more personal and natural way, regardless of their physical location, potentially reducing feelings of isolation and loneliness.

Such service implies the transmission of 3D models of people and objects over the internet, allowing for a high-fidelity, interactive 3D representation of remote locations or people to be viewed in a mixed reality environment. This requires the ability to quickly process and transmit large amounts of data, including video, audio, and 3D models. In this intent, edge computing would allow for real-time processing of the video and audio data captured by the cameras and microphones at the source location. This would allow for the 3D models of people and objects to be generated and transmitted in real-time, rather than having to wait for the data to be sent to a centralized location for processing. Additionally, edge computing could be used to perform advanced computer vision and machine learning techniques, such as object and gesture recognition, on the video and audio data to enhance the overall holoportation experience.

In this respect, 6GENABLERS-AI aims at bridging the gap in holoportation and its intelligent orchestration by i) Distributing the holoportation service functions over the Edge-cloud continuum and ii) Developing native AI pipelines to automate the AI-enabled orchestration lifecycle, enabling a fast adaptation to the dynamicity of the holoportation service. This deliverable analyses the holoportation intelligent orchestration use case and defines the requirements thereof.

2 Holographic Teleportation: State-of-the-Art Review

In this section, we review the literature of holographic-type communications (HTC) and analyse their gaps in terms of both the service technological enablers as well as the corresponding intelligent orchestration.

2.1 State-of-the-art

In their work¹, the authors have introduced a lightweight Social VR platform, which provides three key features. First, it enables a real-time integration of remote users in shared virtual environments, using realistic volumetric representations. Second, it supports a seamless integration of heterogeneous media formats, including 3D scenarios, dynamic volumetric representation of users and (live/stored) stereoscopic 2D and 180°/360° videos. Third, it allows low-latency interaction between the volumetric users and a video-based presenter (Chroma keying), and a dynamic control of the media layout to adapt to the session's evolution.

On the other hand, a 5G MEC framework for enabling remote production of live holographic teleportation services has been presented and evaluated in². By placing complex media processing at remote Edge server which has powerful processing ability, local 5G client can focus on collecting data from camera and leveraging the 5G NR uplink to transfer the raw data to network Edge. Extensive evaluations have been conducted in a real-life 5G test network in terms of achievable throughput, FPS, impact of transport layer protocol, radio condition and the application settings in different scenarios. The results indicate that low resolution levels (e.g., HD) can be well supported with satisfactory performance via 5G radio, with a stable FPS and throughput, and low frame delay.

Besides, a multi-source teleportation application where frames synchronisation is highly required has been introduced³. Since the frames do not arrive at the MEC server on-time, time gap between frames increases as network distance between source and MEC server increases which introduces motion misalignment. Results of experiment proves that after applying synchronization mechanism time gap between frames pair has been reduced by making use of fixed synchronisation window, frame pair time gap value and cached frame.

¹ S. F. Langa, M. M. Climent, G. Cernigliaro and D. Rincón Rivera, "Toward Hyper-Realistic and Interactive Social VR Experiences in Live TV Scenarios," in *IEEE Transactions on Broadcasting*, vol. 68, no. 1, pp. 13-32, March 2022, doi: 10.1109/TBC.2021.3123499

² P. Qian, V. S. H. Huynh, N. Wang, S. Anmulwar, D. Mi and R. R. Tafazolli, "Remote Production for Live Holographic Teleportation Applications in 5G Networks," in *IEEE Transactions on Broadcasting*, vol. 68, no. 2, pp. 451-463, June 2022, doi: 10.1109/TBC.2022.3161745.

³ S. Anmulwar, N. Wang, A. Pack, V. S. Ha Huynh, J. Yang and R. Tafazolli, "Frame Synchronisation for Multi-Source Holographic Teleportation Applications - An Edge Computing Based Approach," *2021 IEEE 32nd Annual International Symposium on Personal, Indoor and Mobile Radio Communications (PIMRC)*, 2021, pp. 1-6, doi: 10.1109/PIMRC50174.2021.9569710.

An HTC based teleportation platform leveraging cloud-based remote production functions has been presented in⁴, which is supported with newly proposed adaptive frame buffering and end-to-end signalling techniques against network uncertainties and can provide assured user experiences at the public Internet scale.

Figure 1 Gaps in HTC and intelligent orchestration

2.2 Gaps Analysis

In the mind map of Figure 1 we summarise the main gaps in holographic communications as well as in intelligent orchestration. Basically, the current needs and challenges mainly involve:

- Low latency, high uplink and downlink bandwidth and stringent adaptability requirements,
- Modular XR media functions to enable an efficient deployment over the edge to cloud continuum,
- Smart AI-driven orchestration of XR, computing and network resources,
- Dynamic network management and slicing,
- Smart service and network adaptation based on available resources.

⁴ I. Selinis, N. Wang, B. Da, D. Yu and R. Tafazolli, "On the Internet-scale Streaming of Holographic-type Content with Assured User Quality of Experiences," *2020 IFIP Networking Conference (Networking)*, 2020, pp. 136-144.

2.2.1 Gaps in holographic communications

Low Latency is a crucial aspect of holoportation technology as it pertains to the perceived realism of the experience. To ensure low latency transmission and rendering, researchers are working to minimize the delay between the capture and display of holographic content. This requires advanced algorithms and high-speed networks to achieve the desired results.

Another important factor is the **high quality of the reconstructed 3D models**. The accuracy and quality of the models can be affected by factors such as the resolution, texture quality, and the complexity of the model. Researchers are working to ensure high-quality reconstructions, taking into consideration the various factors that could impact the quality of the models.

The handling of large scale and **high dynamic range content** is another challenge faced by researchers. This requires advanced algorithms and hardware to process the large amounts of data that need to be transmitted and stored. However, this also poses security and privacy risks, and researchers are working on ways to address these issues to ensure the privacy and security of the users.

Assured User **Quality of Experience** is also a crucial aspect of holoportation technology. Researchers are developing algorithms that adapt to the user's device, network, and location to provide an optimal quality of experience for users. This involves considering various factors such as the user's device performance, network speed, and location to ensure that users have a seamless and enjoyable experience.

Standardization is also a crucial aspect of holoportation technology as it ensures compatibility and interoperability between different systems. Researchers are working on developing standards for the transmission and streaming of holographic content, which will be important in ensuring a seamless experience for users, regardless of the device or system they are using.

Finally, **security and privacy** are a major concern in the development of holoportation technology. Researchers are working to ensure the security and privacy of the holographic content and the personal information of the users. This involves taking various measures to secure the data transmission and storage, as well as protecting the personal information of users.

2.2.2 Gaps in intelligent orchestration

AI is not currently built into wireless networks as it requires significant infrastructure changes—hindered by lack of standardization, complexity, limited resources, security concerns and cost. Many existing wireless networks were built before the widespread use of AI and were not designed to support its integration. Additionally, incorporating AI into wireless networks requires significant resources, such as computational power and memory. A first step toward intelligence has been to incorporate AI as external functions in the network.

On the other hand, intelligent orchestration techniques aim to optimize the allocation of resources and tasks in a distributed system in order to minimize perceived latency for

the end user. In this respect, **predictive modelling** is a critical aspect of resource allocation and optimization that depends also on the accuracy of predicting the resource and task requirements. Furthermore, **optimizing for multiple objectives** such as minimizing latency, maximizing throughput, and minimizing resource utilization can present a complex problem, as current orchestration techniques may struggle to find the optimal balance. Additionally, some tasks, such as machine learning and AI workloads, may be non-deterministic and difficult to predict, adding an extra layer of complexity to the optimization process. To address these challenges, intelligent orchestration techniques must be able to **adapt to changing workloads** and resource requirements in real-time, ensuring that the system continues to operate effectively. Moreover, handling large scale distributed systems with multiple nodes and tasks can pose a challenge for orchestration techniques, as they may not always be able to scale to meet the demands of the system. In many cases, incorporating **domain-specific knowledge** into orchestration decisions can make the process more informed and effective, rather than relying solely on general-purpose algorithms.

Overall, while current orchestration techniques have made significant progress in reducing latency and improving performance, there is still room for improvement in many areas, especially when it comes to making more accurate predictions and optimizing for multiple objectives. Besides, **the key to achieve the ultra-automation of future 6G networks is to design a flexible and adaptable 6G network architecture that can natively support the deployment and execution of AI pipelines as needed**, and that can be easily scaled up and down as required as well as dynamically placed in the Edge-to-cloud continuum, making it capable of enabling the decentralisation and the intelligence level natively needed by the 6G system.

3 Use Case Description

In this section, we first provide a description of the use case in terms of the required equipment to setup it and their dependencies. We then introduce the distributed architecture of the holoportation functions, such as synchronisation, multi-sensor fusion and volumetric video encoding. We finally present the AIOps-enabled resource management needed for the orchestration of the holoportation service.

3.1 Setup

The key idea is to offload prohibitive holographic content production functions from end user premises to the 6G Edge domain in order to concretely reduce the cost of running such heavy applications on the user side. Figure 2 depicts an overview of the holographic teleportation solution. To enable 6DoF video, a remote object is surrounded by multiple sensor cameras in order to be captured into a 3D hologram. Each sensor camera is locally connected to a computer acting as a client whose responsibility is to capture sensor camera data, process local point clouds and produce continuous frames before sending them to the server using asynchronous Socket APIs. Examples of sensor cameras are Microsoft Azure Kinect and Kinect v2. They support a variety of frame rates and resolutions from both RGB and depth sensors. On the other hand, the application server deployed at the Edge oversees aggregating, filtering, synchronizing and merging the frames from the clients to produce a 3D hologram object. This hologram can be stored as a single volumetric file (e.g., ply or bin file format) for later usage or more importantly to be live streamed to the user equipment (UEs)—such as Microsoft HoloLens 2 or any AR/VR supported smartphones—to be viewed as a 6DoF content. Both client and server can be based on a software such as the open-source Livescan3d.

Figure 2 Holographic teleportation

It is also noteworthy that, thanks to Network Function Virtualization (NFV), the application server function can be virtualized and flexibly deployed at any location of the network including mobile Edge. In this regard, the AIOps produced artifacts—for resource predictions or VNF scaling and placement—can be deployed close to the server function to reduce the reaction time to holo-teleportation computation load variations. Specifically, changes in the client-server traffic pattern can e.g., trigger the re-training of the AI resource prediction models.

3.2 Service dependencies

Since the UE cannot run computationally prohibitive frame processing, a client server distributed architecture is required. The key idea is to offload complex holographic content production functions from end user premises to the 5G edge cloud in order to substantially reduce the cost of running such applications on the user side. Figure 2 presents a basic illustration of the solution for 5G edge computing enabled teleportation operations, where the teleportation content production is made into a virtual function hosted by the 5G multi-access edge computing (MEC) node. A real-life testing is based on off-the-shelf Kinect Azure DK cameras and significantly adapted to the teleportation platform based on the original open-source point-cloud system⁵. Point-cloud media are typically generated by synthesizing the videos captured simultaneously by multiple RGB-depth cameras located at different angles around the object and in general a denser camera setup results in a higher point cloud video quality⁶.

The solution to this issue is to apply frame synchronization/buffering directly at the UE side, however there are two limitations for this option: (1) Head mounted devices, which are mainly used for content display, normally do not have very high processing power and storage for handling such high-end teleportation media, and (2) in case of a large number of audience receiving the common stream, it is not efficient to have every single UE to perform dedicated frame synchronization operations. The dependencies of holoportation service are as follows:

- High-quality 3D scanning and modelling: In order to transmit realistic and accurate 3D models of people and objects, high-quality 3D scanning and modelling technology is required.
- High bandwidth: Holoportation application need to transmit tremendous amounts of data that can go from few tens of megabytes to terabytes of data per second. Hence, there is a pressing need for high bandwidth infrastructures. The bandwidth requirements for a real-time transmission of a single hologram needs up to 50Mbps even with compression. In more realistic use-cases with multiple holograms and complex virtual environments (with hundreds of objects), the needed amount of bandwidth will increase exponentially to hundreds of megabits.
- Low latency: Holoportation is highly interactive and hence require high-precision, predictable and ultra-low latency. The visual sense requires less than 10ms latency between successive pictures.
- Synchronization and Interactivity: Holoportation may require multiple flows to be synchronized (i.e., multi-flow synchronization), that is to ensure that the generated data from different sources arrive at the destination within a specific interval of time or even at a particular point of time. As this definition suggests, these flows might originate from different sources, which makes multi-flow synchronization a daunting challenge requiring high-precision control of the data delivery over the network.

⁵ M. Kowalski, J. Naruniec, and M. Daniluk, "Livescan3d: A Fast and Inexpensive 3d Data Acquisition System for Multiple Kinect v2 Sensors," Proc. International Conference on 3D Vision, 2015, <https://github.com/MarekKowalski/LiveScan3D>

⁶ Z. Liu, Q. Li, X. Chen, C. Wu, S. Ishihara, J. Li, and Y. Ji, "Point Cloud Video Streaming: Challenges and Solutions", IEEE Network, Vol. 35, Issue 5, 2021

- High-performance computing: Holoportation generates and consumes tremendous amounts of data that need to be processed at run-time before or after their transmission or even on their way to the destination. Naturally, the type of processing will mainly depend on the application type (e.g., object recognition, movement detection, data compression, data mining, video manipulation, video rendering, encryption)
- Holoportation-specific protocols: Holoportation requires the use of specialized protocols for the transmission and rendering of 3D models, which is an important aspect for this service⁷.
- Video conferencing service integration: Holoportation technology often makes use of video conferencing services to enable collaboration, and that service must be integrated to the holoportation solution in order to work.

3.3 Architecture

The architecture is structured into modular components and provided as a Software-as-a-Service (SaaS), including client libraries, well-defined interfaces and cloud-based components, like Session Orchestrators (lifecycle and session management, media orchestration...) and an XR Multipoint Control Unit (MCU). In this context, this use case will provide key toward 6G technological contributions in the fields of network communications, edge continuum infrastructure, virtualization and AI-powered orchestration to overcome the current challenges and limitations.

Figure 3 Frame synchronisation at Edge server

⁷ M.F. Zhani, H. ElBakoury, "FlexNGIA: A Flexible Internet Architecture for the Next-Generation Tactile Internet." J Netw Syst Manage 28, 751–795 (2020).

3.3.1 Synchronisation

In addition to the conventional network requirements for supporting holographic teleportation applications such as high bandwidth, it can be inferred that data synchronisation in supporting multi-source-based teleportation operations will also play an essential role for assuring user Quality of Experiences (QoE) as depicted in Figure 3. Specifically, it is required that teleportation content frames originated from each source object with the same frame creation time should arrive at the receiver side within a stringent time window in order to avoid perceived motion misalignment between these source objects⁸.

It is expected that human being's tolerance on such motion misalignment may depend on specific application scenarios. For instance, in case of casual chatting without significant body movement, frame synchronisation error may not be an essential issue. However, considering other scenarios with higher degree of body movement for instance, there is higher chance that such body motion misalignment can be more easily detected by human eyes at the viewer side. On the network side, there are multiple factors that may contribute to potential frame synchronisation errors in multi-source teleportation at the Internet scale, including the network distance/latency between individual sources to the viewer side, their path load conditions as well as the frame production conditions on the source side.

As mentioned above, it is more convenient to perform teleportation frame synchronization at the 5G mobile edge that covers the audience behind the MEC (Figure 2). Once the incoming frames have been synchronized at the 5G MEC, they are streamed seamlessly to the local UE in the session, and thanks to the deterministic data transmission capability of 5G NR (downlink), further disruptions on frame synchronization over the last wireless mile to the UE, will be very low. Our solution is able to bring down the magnitude of second level of motion misalignment to sub 100ms.

3.3.2 Multi-Sensor Fusion

In the context of holoportation, multi-sensor fusion is used to create a rich and detailed 3D representation of the person or object being transmitted, including their appearance, motion, and audio. By combining data from multiple sensors (cameras, depth sensors, and microphones), it is possible to capture a more complete and accurate representation of the scene, including details such as the shape, texture, and color of objects and surfaces, as well as the movements and sounds of the person or object being transmitted. Additionally, multi-sensor fusion can also help to overcome limitations and challenges associated with individual sensors, such as occlusions, noise, and resolution, by combining the information from multiple sensors to create a more robust and accurate representation of the scene.

3.3.3 Volumetric Video Encoding

Volumetric video encoding is a method of representing the 3D formation of objects and scenes in a video format. The techniques used for volumetric video encoding vary depending on the specific requirements of the application, but some of the most used

⁸ S. Anmulwar, N. Wang, A. Pack, V. S. H. Huynh, J. Yang, R. Tafazolli, "Frame Synchronisation for Multi-Source Holographic Teleportation Applications-An Edge Computing Based Approach", *Proc. IEEE PIMRC 2021*

methods include Light Field Encoding, Point Cloud Encoding, Voxel-based Encoding, Mesh-based Encoding, and Image-based Encoding. Light Field Encoding captures the light field information of a scene, including the direction of light rays, to create a 3D representation. Point Cloud Encoding involves capturing the 3D geometry of a scene as a set of points and encoding the point cloud data in a compact format. Voxel-based Encoding encodes the volumetric information of a scene as a grid of 3D voxels, with each voxel representing a unit of volume. Mesh-based Encoding involves capturing the 3D geometry of a scene as a set of interconnected triangles and encoding the mesh data in a compact format. Image-based Encoding encodes the volumetric information of a scene as a set of 2D images, with each image representing a slice of the 3D volume. Each of these techniques has its own strengths and limitations, and the choice of encoding method will depend on the specific requirements of the application.

3.4 AIOps-Enabled Resource Orchestration

As an enabler of holoportation, resource allocation as well as VNF placement and scaling play an important role in reducing latency by strategically positioning functions within a network architecture to minimize the distance between them and/or assure the allocation of required resources. By placing holographic service’s VNFs (encoding, reconstruction, fusion, frame alignment...) closer to the holograms source, the amount of data that needs to be transmitted across the different technological domains—i.e., RAN, Edge and Cloud—is reduced, leading to lower latency and improved network performance. Additionally, VNF placement/scaling can also optimize network traffic flow and reduce the number of network hops, further reducing latency and improving network efficiency. By placing AI functions closer to the controlled VNFs, the reaction time—to potential changes in the conditions of the holographic-type communication or the arrival of new monitoring data—can be dramatically reduced. Indeed, as exemplified by Figure 4, the AIOps framework manages the lifecycle of AI models by continuously monitoring their performance, triggering re-training and delivering the artifacts to the right TDs, swiftly responding to service dynamics. This means that the models’ update, and deployment time should be lower than the HTC service granularity.

Figure 4 AIOps-enabled resource orchestration

4 Use Case Requirements

This section describes both the functional and non-functional requirements of the use-case. The formers concern what the system must accomplish while the latter are relevant to the attributes of the system, including e.g., scalability and interoperability.

4.1 Functional Requirements

Functional requirements refer to a set of specifications that outline the tasks that a system must be capable of performing, as well as the way in which those tasks should be carried out. These specifications define the functions, features, and abilities that are essential for a system or software application to satisfy the requirements of its users.

The following table sums up all the details that are mandatory to offer the greatest holoportation experience in terms of quality and content⁹.

Table 1 Holoportation functional requirements

Functional Requirement	Description
Holoportation experience	An end user should have an experience that visually and acoustically allows to perceive and understand the other participants' body language expressions. The level of detail of end-user's representation in the virtual space of holoportation must allow the recognition of facial expressions
Holoportation content visual quality	The virtual character representation must be detailed enough to allow for the recognition of facial expressions
Holoportation content	The representations of the rendered characters, inside the virtual space of holoportation, must be able to retarget their gaze according to the end-user's viewpoint. The representations of the rendered pre-rigged characters, inside the virtual space of holoportation, must be able to retarget pointing gestures
Active watch	The end user inside the virtual space of holoportation must be able to become a character within the storyline that is being projected
Movement	The end user inside the virtual space of holoportation must be able to move 6DoF
Derived actions	The end-user's actions inside the virtual space of holoportation must lead to changes in the storyline that is being projected

⁹ Gianluca Cernigliaro, Guillermo Calahorra, Bart Kevelham, Vincent Lepec, & Pablo Cesar. (2020). VRTogether Project, D2.3 - User scenarios, requirements and architecture (3.0). Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.4439817>

Pattern recognition interaction	The holoportation platform must support multi modal pattern recognition mechanics for changing the storyline according to user's choices
Pointing interaction	The holoportation must be able to recognize pointing gestures of end users and change the storyline accordingly
Speech interaction	The holoportation platform must be able to recognize the speech of end users and change the storyline accordingly
Interactive character	The system should integrate and use interactive character animation
Configuration	The holoportation platform orchestration component must manage sessions where at least 2 end users participate in a virtual space. The holoportation platform orchestration component should support at least two parallel sessions
Holoportation scenario	The holoportation platform must allow 10 end users to simultaneously be in the same virtual space
Latency	MUST achieve an end to end (capture to projection) latency that is lower than 100 ms.
Compression	The Holoportation platform SHOULD support point cloud compression of arbitrary topology and be able to achieve a compression ratio of up to 1:30 for textured mesh (3D geometry and textures) content
Synchronisation	The Holoportation play-out component's native player SHOULD support synchronisation between different input formats with less than 100 ms of delay

4.2 Non-Functional Requirements

Non-functional requirements are a set of specifications that detail the characteristics, attributes, and qualities of a system or software application, as opposed to its specific functional capabilities. These requirements pertain to the general performance, quality, and usability of the system or software application, rather than its particular functionalities and features.

The non-functional requirements of the use-case are listed as follows:

Table 2 Holoportation non-functional requirements

Non-Functional Requirement	Description
Scalability	The implementation of the use case should be scalable and allow for the automatic admission of multiple concurrent AR users/sessions/slices without modifying the architecture.
Interoperability	The setup of the use case should be interoperable with any type of

	user device/AR kit
Modularity	The implementation should be modular to a great extent in such a way the upgrade of one component can be independently done without affecting the other components.
Quality assessment	The Holoportation platform SHOULD be able to evaluate the expected quality of experience according to the objective metrics
Content visual quality	The Holoportation platform MUST support playback of end-user's representation of at least 960x540 pixels

5 KPIs

Measuring the quality of a holoportation service requires looking at several different metrics. One important metric is image quality, which refers to the resolution and clarity of the images that are transmitted during the holoportation process. A high image quality is important for a realistic and immersive experience. Another important metric is latency, which refers to the amount of time it takes for the images to be transmitted from one location to another. Low latency is crucial for a smooth and realistic experience. Bandwidth, which refers to the amount of data that can be transmitted at one time, is also important for a high-quality holoportation experience. A higher bandwidth allows for higher resolution images and reduces the chances of dropped frames. Interactivity, which refers to the ability for people in different locations to interact with each other in real-time, is also an important aspect of a high-quality holoportation service. Immersiveness, which refers to the level of realism of the holoportation experience, including how realistic the images are, how well the sound is synced, and how well the experience mimics being in the same physical location, is also a crucial metric for the quality of holoportation service. User satisfaction, which refers to how happy users are with the overall holoportation experience, is also an important measure of quality. Finally, scalability, which refers to the ability of the holoportation service to handle many users at the same time, and the ability to scale to different platforms and devices, is also a crucial metric for quality holoportation service.

The AI-enabled holo-teleportation performance can be measured by a set of key performance indicators (KPIs) that capture some functional requirements and are listed in Table 3:

Table 3 Holoportation KPIs

KPI	Range
Frame per Second (FPS)	> 30 FPS
Server-side perceived throughput per second	30 to 50 Mbps (compressed) ¹⁰ , 100 Gbps to 1 Tbps (raw) ¹¹
Frame delay	< 50–100 ms end-to-end latency and <15 ms motion-to-photon latency ¹²

¹⁰ "Microsoft holoportation. <https://www.microsoft.com/en-us/research/project/holoportation-3/>," Accessed: 5 Feb. 2023.

¹¹ X. Xu, Y. Pan, P. P. M. Y. Lwin, and X. Liang, "3d holographic display and its data transmission requirement," in International Conference on Information Photonics and Optical Communications, Oct 2011, pp. 1–4

¹²T. Rhee, et al., "Augmented virtual teleportation for high-fidelity telecollaboration," IEEE Trans. Vis. Comput. Graph. 2020, 26, 1923–1933

Figure 5 Holoportation KPIs ranges

On the other hand, there is no one-size-fits-all solution when it comes to MLOps KPIs. The metrics that should be monitored depend on the specific goals and environment. The major KPIs to always keep an eye on when deploying ML software in production include:

Table 4 AIOps KPIs

KPI	Description
Model optimization iteration time	Duration of a training iteration
Time to deployment	Time from triggering re-training to artifact deployment in production
API calls for AI as a service	Frequency of AI prediction service calls

6 Conclusion

This deliverable has presented a description of the 6GENABLERS-AI holoportation use case, including an SoA gap analysis, use case setup, dependencies, and architecture, which includes synchronisation, multi-sensor fusion and volumetric video encoding. Moreover, the role of AIOps in the proper holoportation service orchestration has been highlighted. The use case functional and non-functional requirements have been then presented and the related KPIs listed, which involves HTC as well as MLOps metrics. It turns out that AIOps is necessary to adapt the resource allocation and the placement of service VNFs (encoding, synchronisation...) to the dynamic HTC traffic by timely triggering AI models re-training (upon arrival of new data) and delivering the artifacts to the target technological domains (RAN, Edge or Cloud) to be closer to the managed resources.